

EXPERIENCE IN TEACHING CHILDREN TO FIND RIDDLES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONNECTED SPEECH - THE ORGANIZATION OF EXPERIMENTS AND ITS METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted reading lessons in primary school, use of pedagogical technologies in the process, new interactive methods the positive importance of use is highlighted. Also from interactive methods samples are recommended and illuminated.

Keywords: primarily school, reading, interactive, explanatory reading, intonation, method, education, expressive reading, art reading.

INTRODUCTION

The use of problem-based learning in teaching is also effective in shaping creative activity. In addition to heuristic or research methods, the process of bringing children into the "laboratory" of creative thinking is also important, as it involves the independent search and discovery of a truth. Problem-based learning has several advantages in this regard:

1. Creating a problem situation by comparing the topics given in the mother tongue textbook, so that each topic studied requires children to compare sounds, words and sentences and make generalizations on this basis. And that, in turn, creates a problem. In children, "Why?" need to find an answer to the question. For example, when studying the topic of "vowels and consonants", the student first names the vowels and consonants correctly, then compares them, forms words with vowels and consonants, and sentences from words, distinguishes them from each other. requires identification.

2. Create a problematic situation by asking problematic questions.

The facilitator begins the lesson by asking a problem:

Emphasize vowels and consonants.

What difference do you notice in pronouncing them?

2. Write a word with six vowels and letters. Try replacing the flour in them with another flour, what changes do you notice?

3. Pronounce consonant sounds. Write the consonants that make up the noise separately, and the consonants that make up the noise only.

An example is set only if the tasks are difficult to complete.

4. Creating problem situations through symbolic images.

This method of creating a problem situation uses symbolic images. For example, you may be asked to create a text on the topic, giving pictures and the name “Melons of Uzbekistan”.

5. The grouping and separation of linguistic phenomena is also important in creating a problem situation. In particular, combining words into specific cells and requiring them to find the specific meaning of a word with a common meaning or the general meaning of a word with a specific meaning can create a problematic situation. For example, there are dozens or even hundreds of nesting boxes for learning tools, fruits, vegetables, trees, and flowers, and the Educator refers the general meaning of the word to the student’s judgment and leaves it to the children to find the remaining words.

1. Vegetables: carrots, ...

2. Teaching aids: books, ... etc.

METHODS

In the development of creative activity, more attention should be paid to the motivational and interesting aspects of education, aimed at developing interest in learning. A characteristic feature of work with children is not their slow adaptation to the weaknesses of their psyche, but the principle of actively influencing their mental development in order for children to be as active as possible. Educators and Caregivers should not be perceived as having the impression that some children’s abilities are average or incompetent or even imperfect. Such children gradually adapt to the ever-accelerating and complex educational process.

Proper and effective organization of lessons in education, of course, affects the learning of children. Another important issue in the development of creative activity is related to the technologically correct design of the lesson by the educator. How to use interactive methods at what stage begins with lesson planning. The design takes place in the following stages.

I- is the concentration phase

II- listening stage

Stage III thinking

These steps will help you to use the interactive methods correctly and in the right place, as well as to increase the efficiency of the lesson.

Concentration phase: in which the Educator identifies the children's initial understanding of a new topic.

Purpose:

- clear, free expression of initial concepts;
- to be able to express one's opinion;
- increase interest in the lesson;

Comprehension Phase: In this case, the educator enriches the new knowledge by summarizing additional teachings to the initial concepts received from the children. That is, the information that the student knows and does not know is supplemented.

The purpose of the identification phase:

- fill the student's understanding with new knowledge based on the initial concepts;
- increase children's interest;
- teaching to analyze and compare;
- describe a new lesson.

Thinking phase: This phase corresponds to the reinforcement part of the lesson. In it, children analyze the initial concepts and information, think and strengthen their knowledge. The children express their views on the lesson and the topic.

RESULTS

A well-organized lesson will pay off, of course. However, it is not possible to increase the effectiveness of a lesson without a thorough study of the methods used at each stage.

Educational standards and norms are traditionally used to assess learning outcomes. The closer a student's results are to the standard, the higher his or her academic performance will be. The amount of knowledge actually acquired and created by the student is not fully controlled, as children's personal knowledge or other out-of-standard knowledge is left out of the traditional school's perspective.

The approach to evaluating learning outcomes in creativity is unique. It is not the degree of achievement of external results that is examined, but often the deviations from it. The main parameter of children's learning outcomes in the assessment of creativity is not the level of compliance with the minimum requirements of the standards, but the level of personal growth of the student.

In traditional education, the student does not participate in the selection of the content of education. In creative activities, the educational effect of the student in

education is involved in the selection of a new content of education; the amount of knowledge, skills, activities, and methods used by the student will not be limited.

It teaches children logical, scientific, didactic, creative thinking.

It makes the teaching material believable, thereby helping the knowledge to become a belief.

He is usually quite impressionable and develops deep intellectual feelings, including an uplifting spirit, a sense of confidence in his own abilities and strengths, so he is interested in children, serious about scientific knowledge in children creates content of interest.

It has been established that the independent "discovery" of the law of truth does not forget the acquired knowledge, and even if the independently generated knowledge is forgotten, it can be quickly restored.

The main purpose of problem-based education is to increase the independence and activity of students, to develop their thinking, to strengthen the application of knowledge in practice in accordance with the requirements of the quality stage of the National Training Program.

That is, the set of knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired through the presentation of a particular topic in the form of a problem is called problem-based learning.

Problem-based learning is:

- Problem
- Problematic question
- Problematic task
- Problem assignment
- Problematic situation.

The problem itself is derived from the Greek word "problem", which means task.

CONCLUSION

Expressing the psychological state of the problem situation-subject, the search for new knowledge and ways of action that prevent the immediate resolution of mental difficulties when faced with a problem, provides them with the difficulties of finding and overcoming the difficulties that arise. This requires a psychological approach to the problem.

For example, the following methods can be used to create problematic situations based on the level of knowledge of the age characteristics of their children:

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